

Policy Evaluation Analysis of Palm Oil as Renewable Energy Resistance Commodities

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Abstract

Since 2004 Indonesia has held the status of a net oil importer. The government's effort to maximize foreign exchange inflow and minimize foreign exchange outflows in relation to the revitalization of palm oil commodities. This study aims to provide an evaluation analysis of the policy on the use of oil palm in supporting national energy security. This study uses the balanced scorecard (BSC) method as an evaluation framework that is integrated with the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) method as a weighting. The policy evaluation on the use of palm oil in supporting national energy security has a value of 80.222% with a Moderate category. This aspect is elaborated in the Learning & Development (P) Criteria value with an evaluation result of 87.359% in the Good category. Energy Supply System Criteria (S) with an evaluation result of 75.788% in the Moderate category. Energy Services Consumers (E) Criteria with evaluation results of 75.452% in the Moderate category. Welfare Criteria (W) with an evaluation result of 82.313% in the Good category.

Key Words : *Evaluasi Kebijakan, Kelapa Sawit, Ketahanan Energi, Balanced Scorecard (BSC), Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)*

INTRODUCTION

Since 2004 Indonesia has held the status of a net oil importer. The condition of net importers is done to meet domestic oil consumption, which cannot be fulfilled by domestic oil production (Badaruddin, 2015). Some of the government's efforts in facing obstacles to achieving energy security by issuing a new energy policy (mixed energy) of 23% in 2025 and 31% in 2050, so that energy needs are no longer dependent on fossil fuel. The threat in the form of a resolution of the European Parliament (EP) in 2021, made the government realize the importance of renewable energy based on plants (biofuels) by utilizing the wealth of natural resources from Crude Palm Oil (CPO) or palm oil (Schader, et al., 2017).

The government's effort to maximize foreign exchange inflow and minimize foreign exchange outflows in relation to the revitalization of palm oil commodities is by issuing policies in the form of an obligation to mix 20 percent biodiesel, hereinafter referred to as mandatory B-20 biodiesel. This obligation is extended to all sectors in effect starting September 1, 2018, with the 2018 biodiesel uptake target of 5.7 million kiloliters (KL). In the long run, this renewable energy from CPO will minimize the predicted threat of net total energy importers by 2027 (Risman, et al., 2017).

Based on these conditions, it is necessary to have an evaluation study of the policy on the use of palm oil in supporting national security. The evaluation is used as an analysis of the extent to which oil palm policy is implemented and as a basis for planning further strategies regarding oil palm to support national energy security. This study aims to provide an evaluation analysis of the policy on the use of oil palm in supporting national energy security. This study uses the balanced scorecard (BSC) method as an evaluation framework that is integrated with the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) method as a weighting.

There are several previous studies in support of this research, including research with the title Replacing Renewable Energy in Iranian Industries Using Optimal Models (Jalalimajidi & Seyedhosseini, 2017). Economic Impacts of Renewable Energy Promotion in Germany (Bohringer, et al., 2017). Canadian Bioenergy Development and EU Influences (Sawatzkya, 2017). The Role of China in Global Energy

Governance (Christoffersen, 2016). Research On Energy Strategy And Chinese Energy Investment In The Middle East (Huang, 2017). The perceived success of energy strategies for South Africa's financial services industry (Westhuizen & Young, 2018). The Energy Policies for Sustainable Economic Growth in Turkey (Gokırmak, 2017).

Previous research on the Balanced Scorecard and Analytical Hierarchy Process, among others, with the title Combining Analytical Hierarchy Process and Simple Multi-Attribute Rating Technique for designing a Sustainable Balanced Scorecard as Strategic Performance Measurement System (Suryaningkusuma, et al., 2018). Integrating the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Balanced Scorecard (BSC) Framework for Sustainable Business in a Software Factory in the Financial Sector (Pérez, et al., 2017). A Model for Performance Evaluation of Digital Game Industry Using Integrated AHP and BSC (Moradi, et al., 2018). Employee Performance Appraisal Model Using Human Resources Scorecard And Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Mutmainah, et al., 2017). Integration of Balanced Scorecard and Analytical Hierarchy Process as a Tool for Determining the Priority of the Program Strategy: Case Study in Dr.Tc.Hillers Maumere Hospital (Dekrita, et al., 2018). Sustainability performance measurement with Analytic Network Process and balanced scorecard: Cuban practical case (Medel-González, et al., 2016).

This paper consists of 4 sections. Section 2 explains the evaluation theory, palm oil as renewable energy, resilience theory, AHP method, balanced scorecard method. Section 3 explains the results and discussion. Section 4 explains the conclusions of the analysis of the evaluation of oil palm policy as renewable energy.

MATERIAL/METHODS

Policy evaluation

Evaluation is aimed at assessing the effectiveness of public policies in order to be accountable to their constituents (Ariyoko & Susilo, 2019). The extent to which objectives are achieved and to see the extent of the gap between expectations and reality. The extent to which objectives are achieved and to see the extent of the gap between expectations and reality (Diaz, et al., 2015).

Policy evaluation is an activity that involves estimating or evaluating policies that cover the substance, implementation and impact of implementing the policy. Policy evaluation can be divided into two different tasks, the first task is to determine the consequences of a policy by describing its impact. While the second task is to assess the success or failure of a policy based on predetermined standards or criteria. Policy evaluation is a matter of fact in the form of measurement and assessment both of the stages of the implementation of the policy and of the outcome (outcome) or impact (impact) of the operation of a particular policy or program, so determining the steps that can be taken in the future (Stufflebeam, 2001).

Public policy evaluation has four functions, such as (Crumpton, et al., 2016):

a. Explanation.

Through evaluation, the reality of program implementation can be portrayed and a generalization can be made of the patterns of relationships between the various dimensions of reality that are observed. From this evaluation, the evaluator can identify problems, conditions, and actors that support the success or failure of the program.

b. Obedience.

Through evaluation, it can be seen whether the actions taken by the actors, both bureaucracy and other actors are in accordance with the standards and procedures set by the policy.

c. Audit.

Through evaluation, it can be seen whether the output actually reaches the target group of the policy, or there are actually leaks or deviations.

d. Accounting.

With an evaluation, it can be seen what the socioeconomic consequences of the policy.

Energy Security

Energy is managed based on the principles of expediency, rationality, efficiency, justice, increasing added value, sustainability, community welfare, preservation of environmental functions, national resilience and integration by prioritizing national capabilities. Energy security not only includes efforts to meet energy needs but also is the ability of people to obtain and utilize energy and consider aspects of energy management, including environmental aspects (Anbumozhi & Kojima, 2019).

In order to support sustainable national development and enhance national resilience, the objectives of energy management include independence, supply, management, energy utilization, efficiency, community access, the energy industry and the environment. From these two articles, it can be concluded that energy security not only includes efforts to fulfill energy needs but also is the ability of people to obtain and utilize energy and consider aspects of energy management, including environmental aspects (Jaelani, et al., 2017).

The International Energy Agency (IEA) defines energy security as the availability of uninterrupted energy sources at an affordable price. The measure used to assess a country is said to have energy security if it has an energy supply for 90 days of oil equivalent import needs. Energy security is considered important because energy is an important component in the production of goods and services. Any form of disruption that can hamper the availability of energy supply in the form of primary fuels (BBM, gas and coal) or electricity can reduce the economic productivity of a region and if the magnitude of the disturbance reaches the national level can make the target of economic growth slip from the set.

Referring to the energy security concept defined by the IEA above and referring to the basic theory of microeconomics, there are three basic components in maintaining the sustainability of energy supply, namely: (1) precision energy demand estimation as a basis for planning the supply of energy supply, (2) reliability (reliability) the supply of energy sought by the business entity, and (3) the price of energy that signals the business entity to enter the energy supply.

Palm Oil as an Alternative Energy

Palm oil is one of the most consumed and produced oils in the world. This cheap, easily produced and very stable oil can be used as a source of biofuel or biodiesel. World palm oil production is dominated by Indonesia and Malaysia. These two countries in total produce around 85-90% of total world palm oil production. Indonesia is the largest producer and exporter of palm oil. Palm oil is one of the plants that have surplus value to meet food in Indonesia. Foodstuffs intended in this case are aimed at palm oil exports as market demand needs. Palm oil exports in the past four years have tended to increase. However, in 2016 it decreased (Amiruddin, et al., 2005).

Palm oil exports have increased between 9.44 to 16.06 percent per year, whereas in 2016, they decreased by 13.96 percent. Furthermore, in 2017 the total export volume increased by 19.45 percent. In 2013 the total export volume reached 22.22 million tons with a total value of US \$ 17.14 billion, in 2017, it increased to 29.07 million tons with a total value of US \$ 20.72 billion. With the production of palm oil in 2017 reaching 34.47 million tons, there is no problem with killing market demand. So that the need for oil as food will not be deficient and can be used as raw material for biodiesel. In terms of energy security, biodiesel is considered a solution to address environmental problems from the use of fossil fuel energy, including climate change (Mancini, et al., 2015).

Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) Method

Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a method for solving an unstructured, complex situation into several components in a hierarchical arrangement, by giving a subjective value about the relative importance of each variable, and determining which variable has the highest priority to influence the outcome of the situation. The decision-making process is basically choosing the best alternative (Wang, 2015). Such as structuring the problem, determining alternatives, determining the likelihood value for the aleatory variable,

setting the value, the time preference requirements, and the specification of risk. No matter how wide the alternative can be determined or the detailed assessment of the probability value, the limitation that still surrounds is the basis of comparison in the form of a single criterion (Cahyaningrum & Rukmi, 2014).

The principle of compiling a hierarchy is to describe and describe the hierarchy, by breaking the problem into separate elements. This is done by breaking down our complex, complex thoughts into parts of the main elements, then these parts into parts, and so on hierarchically. The description of the objectives of the lower hierarchy is basically intended to obtain measurable criteria (Wasike, et al., 2010). Although in fact, this is not always the case. In certain cases, it might be more beneficial to use the objectives at a higher hierarchy in the analysis process. The lower the setting of a goal, the easier it is to set objective measures and criteria. However, there are times when the decision-making analysis process does not require elaboration. So one way to state the measure of achievement is to use a subjective scale.

AHP method can be done with the following steps, likely (Malik, et al., 2013):

- a. Define the problem and determine the desired solution.
- b. Create a hierarchical structure that starts with the main goal.
- c. Make a pairwise comparison matrix that illustrates the relative contribution or influence of each element to the goals or criteria on the same level.
- d. Make a pairwise comparison so that the total rating is as many as $n \times [(n-1) / 2]$ pieces, where n is the number of elements compared.
- e. Calculate eigenvalues and test their consistency.
- f. Repeat steps 3,4, and 5 for all levels of the hierarchy.
- g. Calculates eigenvectors from each pairwise comparison matrix.
- h. Check the consistency of the hierarchy.

Figure 1. Hierarchy Model.

Balanced Scorecard Method

Manufacturing and non-manufacturing industries can use the application of this BSC performance measurement model. For the manufacturing industry, the BSC model is used to measure supply chain management performance in terms of customer satisfaction, cost, and availability and sustainability (Pérez, et al., 2017). Measuring business performance tools of a company considering various methods is Kaplan and Norton (1996) creating the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) as a measure of strategic implementation using 4 (four) generic perspectives, namely financial, customer, internal process, learning and growth perspectives as the following (Dekrita, et al., 2018):

- a. Financial perspective.
This aspect shows whether strategy transformation leads to increased economic success.
- b. Customer perspective.
This aspect shows the customer segment and competitive advantage in its market.
- c. Internal process perspective.

This aspect shows the internal business processes that enable the company to meet customer expectations in the target market and shareholders.

d. Learning and growth perspective.

This aspect shows the infrastructure needed to achieve the objectives of the other three perspectives.

Figure 2. Balanced Scorecard Aspect.

Goal

This study identified and weighted evaluation criteria. This study describes an analysis of energy security policy evaluations. Sources of data obtained from several previous research literature, books and journals. Data is taken from two sources, namely respondents and experts. Expert resources are needed to obtain criteria for weighting data and determining evaluation recommendations. Respondent data is used to obtain an evaluation value of palm oil policy in supporting national energy security.

Flowchart.

Figure 3. Research Flowchart.

Research Methods

This research consists of 3 stages. The first and second stage is the determination and weighting of criteria by experts. Expert is drawn from 6 (six) personnel who are experts in the field of renewable energy and energy security by conducting questionnaires and interviews. The third stage is the evaluation of the policy on palm oil as renewable energy. At this stage, the evaluation of policy evaluations is carried out using respondents' values consisting of 50 personnel spread across several regions. The assessment is done using a Likert scale score of 1-5.

Table 1. Score Analysis of Research.

AHP Score	Likert Score	Percentage (100%)	Description
9	5	91-100	Excellent
7-8	4	81-90	Good
5-6	3	71-80	Moderate
3-4	2	61-70	Weak
1-2	1	0-60	Poor

Table 2. Expert For This Research.

No	Expert	Total
1	Ministry of Research, Technology and Higher Education of the Republic of Indonesia in the Field of Innovation	1 person
2	Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, Renewable Energy	1 person
3	Ministry of Industry	1 person
4	Ministry of Agriculture	1 person
5	Ministry of Transportation	1 person
6	Pertamina as a biofuel distribution operator	1 person

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Determination and Weighting Criteria

Based on the results of the questionnaire and interviews with 6 (six) selected experts, obtained several criteria in evaluating the implementation of the Palm Oil policy as Renewable energy in supporting national security, these criteria include:

Table 3. Criteria of Policy Evaluation.

Criteria	Sub Criteria	Code
Learning & Development (P)	Increased information capital	P1
	increased organizational capital	P2
	HR improvement	P3
Energy Supply System (S)	Improved Operations Management Process	S1
	Improved Customer Management Process	S2
	Improvement of the Innovation Process	S3
	Improved Social Processes and Regulations	S4
Energy Services Consumers (E)	Reduction of energy supply costs	E1
	Alternative energy sources	E2
	Increased energy consumer confidence and community involvement	E3
Welfare (W)	Regional Environmental Quality Improvement	W1
	The increased socio-economic value generated	W2

The next step is to create a hierarchical model from the aspects and criteria of the AHP model based on the table above.

Figure 4. Hierarchy Model of Renewable Energy Policy Evaluation.

Based on the hierarchical picture above, the policy evaluation on the use of palm oil as renewable energy has 4 (four) aspects of the Balanced Scorecard approach. Learning and Development aspects consist of 3 (three) sub-criteria; The Energy Supply System aspect consists of 4 (four) sub-criteria; The Consumer Energy Service aspect consists of 3 (three) sub-criteria; The welfare aspect consists of 2 (two) sub-criteria.

Criteria Weighting.

Table 4. Result of Criteria Weighting.

Criteria	Sub Criteria	Code	Local	Total
Learning & Development (P) (0,329)	Increased information capital	P1	0,198	0,065
	increased organizational capital	P2	0,312	0,103
	HR improvement	P3	0,490	0,161
Energy Supply System (S) (0,329)	Improved Operations Management Process	S1	0,296	0,097
	Improved Customer Management Process	S2	0,246	0,081
	Improvement of the Innovation Process	S3	0,282	0,093
	Improved Social Processes and Regulations	S4	0,177	0,058
Energy Services Consumers (E) (0,20)	Reduction of energy supply costs	E1	0,198	0,040
	Alternative energy sources	E2	0,490	0,098
	Increased energy consumer confidence and community involvement	E3	0,312	0,062
Welfare (W) (0,142)	Regional Environmental Quality Improvement	W1	0,333	0,047
	Increased socio-economic value generated	W2	0,667	0,095

Figure 5. Graph of Weighting Criteria.

Based on table xx, the Learning and Development Aspect consists of 3 (three) sub-criteria with a weight of 0.329; The Energy Supply System aspect consists of 4 (four) sub-criteria with a weight of 0.329; The Consumer Energy Service aspect consists of 3 (three) sub-criteria with a weight of 0.20; The welfare aspect consists of 2 (two) sub-criteria with a weight of 0.142.

After knowing the weight of each criterion that becomes the benchmark in the evaluation, the next step is to evaluate the policy of using palm oil as renewable energy. The evaluation starts with an assessment of each of the benchmarks used in each aspect of the BSC. Policy evaluation will be better if the results achieved have a value that is close to the evaluation target.

Table 5. Evaluation Result of Learning & Development (P) Aspect.

Criteria	Weight	Score	Result	%	Description
Increased information capital	0,065	4,519	0,294	90,377	Good
increased organizational capital	0,103	4,490	0,461	89,792	Good
HR improvement	0,161	4,108	0,663	82,152	Good
Evaluation Result	0,329		1,417	87,441	Good

The evaluation of energy security policies in the Learning & Development (P) aspect consists of three criteria, namely Increasing information capital, increasing organizational capital, and increasing HR. Criteria Increase information capital has an evaluation result value of 90.377% with the Good category. The criteria for increasing organizational capital have an evaluation result value of 89.792% with the Good category. HR improvement criteria have an evaluation result value of 82.152% with the Good category.

Table 6. Evaluation Result of the energy supply system (S) Aspect.

Criteria	Weight	Score	Result	%	Description
Improved Operations Management Process	0,097	3,487	0,339	69,735	Weak
Improved Customer Management Process	0,081	4,030	0,326	80,60	Moderate
Improvement of the Innovation Process	0,093	3,512	0,326	70,238	Weak
Improved Social Processes and Regulations	0,058	4,178	0,243	83,568	Good
Evaluation Result	0,329		1,234	76,035	Moderate

The evaluation of energy security policy in the aspect of energy supply system (S) consists of four criteria, namely Improved Operations Management Processes, Improved Customer Management Processes, Improved Innovation Processes, and Improved Social Processes & Regulations. Criteria for Improvement of Operations Management Process has an evaluation result value of 69.735% with the category of Weak. Criteria for Improvement of Customer Management Processes have an evaluation value of 80.60% with a

Moderate category. Criteria for Improvement of the Innovation Process has an evaluation result value of 70.238% with the category of Weak. Criteria for Improvement of Social Processes & Regulations have an evaluation result value of 83.568% with the Good category.

Table 7. Evaluation Result of Energy Services Consumers (E) Aspect.

Criteria	Weight	Score	Result	%	Description
Reduction of energy supply costs	0,040	3,335	0,132	66,699	Weak
Alternative energy sources	0,098	3,778	0,371	75,568	Moderate
Increased energy consumer confidence and community involvement	0,062	4,261	0,266	85,223	Good
Evaluation Result	0,200		0,769	75,830	Moderate

The evaluation of energy security policies in the aspects of Energy Services Consumers (E) consists of three criteria, namely Reduction of energy supply costs, Alternative additional energy sources, and increased energy consumer confidence & community involvement. Criteria Reduction in energy supply costs has an evaluation result value of 66.699% with the Weak category. Criteria Alternative alternative energy sources have an evaluation result value of 75.568% with the Moderate category. Criteria for increasing energy consumer confidence & community involvement have an evaluation result value of 85.223% with the Good category.

Table 8. Evaluation Result of Welfare (W) aspect.

Criteria	Weight	Score	Result	%	Description
Regional Environmental Quality Improvement	0,047	4,207	0,199	84,134	Good
Increased socio-economic value generated	0,095	4,025	0,380	80,492	Moderate
Evaluation Result	0,142		0,579	82,313	Good

The evaluation of energy security policy on the Welfare (W) aspect consists of two criteria, namely Regional Environmental Quality Improvement and Increased socio-economic value produced. Regional Environmental Quality Improvement Criteria has an evaluation result value of 84.134% in the Good category. Criteria, The resulting increase in socioeconomic value, has an evaluation result value of 80.492% with the Moderate category.

Table 9. Evaluation Result of Policy Implementation for Palm Oil as a Renewable Energy to Support Energy Security.

Criteria	Weight	Score	Result	%	Description
Learning & Development (P)	0,329	4,368	1,437	87,359	Good
Energy Supply System (S)	0,329	3,789	1,247	75,788	Moderate
Energy Services Consumers (E)	0,200	3,773	0,755	75,452	Moderate
Welfare (W)	0,142	4,116	0,583	82,313	Good
Evaluation Result	1,000		4,023	80,228	Moderate

Based on table xx, the evaluation of policies on the use of palm oil in supporting national energy security has a value of 80.278% with a Moderate category. This aspect is elaborated in the Learning & Development (P) Criteria with an evaluation result of 87.359% in the Good category. Energy Supply System Criteria (S) with an evaluation result of 75.788% in the Moderate category. Energy Services Consumers (E) Criteria with evaluation results of 75.452% in the Moderate category. Welfare Criteria (W) with an evaluation result of 82.313% in the Good category.

Figure 6. Graph of Policy Evaluation Result.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results of the evaluation of the use of palm oil in supporting energy security by using the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) and Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) approach, it can be seen that the Learning and Development Aspect consists of 3 (three) sub-criteria with a weight of 0.329; The Energy Supply System aspect consists of 4 (four) sub-criteria with a weight of 0.329; The Consumer Energy Service aspect consists of 3 (three) sub-criteria with a weight of 0.20; The welfare aspect consists of 2 (two) sub-criteria with a weight of 0.142.

The policy evaluation on the use of palm oil in supporting national energy security has a value of 80.222% with a Moderate category. This aspect is elaborated in the Learning & Development (P) Criteria value with an evaluation result of 87.359% in the Good category. Energy Supply System Criteria (S) with an evaluation result of 75.788% in the Moderate category. Energy Services Consumers (E) Criteria with evaluation results of 75.452% in the Moderate category. Welfare Criteria (W) with an evaluation result of 82.313% in the Good category.

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